

EFFECTS OF TOMATO CULTIVARS AND PLANTING DATES ON THE LEAF CURL VIRUS DISEASE

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted at Horticulture Research Scheme (Vegetable) VNMKV, Parbhani during Rabi, 2017-18 and Summer 2018-19 to detect the effect of different dates of planting and cultivars of tomato on leaf curl virus disease. The effect of planting dates/seasons and tomato varieties on tomato leaf curl virus disease indicated that the crop grown during summer season suffered most severely which consequently caused drastic reduction in whitefly population, disease incidence and fruit yield than that of crop grown during Rabi. During summer season, of the three planting dates, the crop planted on 17/01/2018 (D1) was found to escape with comparatively least average whitefly population and leaf curl disease incidence as well as significantly highest fruit yield of 152.0 q/ha was noted in Arka Rakshak and 91.8 q/ha in Pusa Ruby. During Rabi season, of the three planting dates, the crop planted on 17/10/2017 (D1) was found to escape significantly least average whitefly population and leaf curl disease incidence as well as significantly highest fruit yield of 182.0 q/ha was observed in Arka Rakshak and 163.0 q/ha in Pusa Ruby. A strong positive correlation was obtained between vector population dynamics and disease incidence in tomato plants.

Keywords: Planting season, Tomato leaf curl, Whitefly, Cultivars.

Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is an importance and most widely grown vegetable crop of both tropics and sub tropics of the world, belonging to the family solanaceae and ranks second among vegetables. The genus *Lycopersicon* consists of nine closely related species. The center of origin of tomato is Peru and Mexico in Central and South America. Tomato has been introduced in India during 19th century from Europe. India account for about 8% of the world tomato production and is the 3rd largest producer after china and USA. The major tomato producing states in India are Maharashtra, Bihar, Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, Orissa, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh and Assam. Tomato cultivation has becomes increasingly popular in India because of its varied climatic condition and high nutritive value. The incidence of ToLCV in tomato growing areas of Karnataka ranged from 17-100 per cent in different seasons (Saikia and Muniyappa, 1989). Yield loss exceeds 90 per cent, when infection occurred within four weeks after transplanting in the field (Sastry and Singh, 1973). According to Díaz-Pendón et al. (2021), symptoms of ToLCVD include a decrease in leaf area, upward curling, stunted growth, puckering of leaflets, vein clearing, abnormal shoot proliferation, deformation of leaf lets, inward and outward leaf curling, bushy appearance, internode reduction, and a reduction in yield quantity as well as quality by producing small-sized fruit or no fruit formation at all. In the fall of 2022, ToLCNDV was isolated from various cucurbit crops grown in Shanghai, Jiangsu Province, and Zhejiang Province, which are in China's southeast coastal regions. An infection of approximately 650 hectares resulted in economic losses of about US\$15 million (Gu et al. 2023; Zeng et al. 2023). The vector life period is shortest during May to September than December to February due to variation in temperature. The incidence and rate of spread of the disease are directly proportional to the whitefly population present in the environment (Mehta et al., 1994). The current investigations focused on the effects of various planting season dates and tomato leaf curl virus cultivars in light of the economic significance of the tomato crop and the yield losses caused by tomato leaf virus disease.

Material and Methods**Effect of planting dates and tomato varieties**

The effect planting dates and tomato cultivars/varieties on whitefly population and incidence of tomato leaf curl virus disease and its corresponding effect on fruit yield were studied. The field experiment was planned during Rabi 2017 and Summer 2018 at Research farm of the Horticulture Research Scheme (Vegetable), VNMKV, Parbhani. A total three planting dates viz., 17/10/2017, 2/11/2017 and 16/01/2018 (Rabi, 2017) and 17/01/2018, 2/02/2018 and 18/02/2018 (Summer, 2018) as main treatments and two tomato cv. Pusa Ruby and Arka Rakshak as sub- treatments were selected.

Experimental details (Rabi 2017 and Summer 2018)

Design	:	F.R.B.D
Replication	:	Three
Plot size	:	3.0x3.15m ²
Spacing	:	60x45m ²

Treatments :**Main treatments (Planting Dates)**

Rabi, 2017	Summer, 2018
D1:17/10/2017	D1:17/01/2018
D2:2/11/2017	D2:2/02/2018
D3:18/11/2017	D3:18/02/2018

Sub- treatments (Two tomato cultivars)

- V1:Pusa Ruby (susceptible)
V2: Arka Rakshak (tolerant)

Thirty days old seedlings of Pusa Ruby (V₁) and Arka Rakshak (V₂) were transplanted in the field plots at respective days of transplanting during both the seasons of Rabi, 2017 and Summer, 2018. The crop was grown as per recommended package of practices. Except fungicidal application, plant protection measures for insect pest management were undertaken. As and when needed, the protective irrigations to the crop were given during both the seasons. The observations in respect of vector population and disease incidence were recorded. Whiteflies counts were recorded as per the method modified by Sipell et al. (1982). The whiteflies were counted early in morning before 7.30 A.M. from three leaves i.e. top, middle and bottom leaves of three randomly selected plants of each treatment. The whitefly count was recorded from 15 days after transplanting with an interval of 15 days. The data on vector population was transformed by using Poison formula $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$, where x is the average number of vectors and analyzed statistically. The plant showing infections of tomato leaf curl virus (TLCV) were marked at different growth stages i.e. from 30 days after transplanting to 60 days after transplanting with an interval of 15 days. The percentage of disease incidence was worked out. The weather parameter like temperature, relative humidity, rainfall, rainy days, and wind velocity were correlated and regression function was worked out between number of whiteflies population and disease incidence studied.

Result and Discussion**Effect of planting dates/ season and tomato varieties on tomato leaf curl virus disease.****Whitefly population and planting date**

Result Table 1 and 2 revealed that in all the three planting dates during Rabi 2017-18 and Summer 2018-19 tomato leaf curl virus disease was first noticed appear after two weeks of transplanting of the tomato cultivars in the field. It was observed that the planting dates significantly influenced the whitefly population and percentage

disease incidence in both of the tomato cultivars grown and was found to increase steadily with age of the crop. In *Rabi* crop planting three dates, significantly maximum overall average whitefly population was 1.41, 1.52, 1.88 and 2.15 whitefly/leaf was recorded at 15, 30, 45 and 60 days after transplanting (DAT), respectively in the crop transplanted on D₃ (18/11/2017). This was followed by the crop transplanted on D₂ (2/11/2017) which recorded overall average whitefly population of 1.15, 1.38, 1.51, and 1.69 whitefly/ leaf at 15, 30, 45 and 60 DAT, respectively. The crop transplanted on D₁ (17/10/2017) was found to suffer less by the tomato leaf curl virus of tomato whitefly population observed at various interval was found to be significantly higher in the crop transplanted on 18/11/2017 (D₃); whereas, it was at par in the crop transplanted on 2/11/2017(D₂) and 18/11/2017(D₃). In Summer crop planting three dates, significantly maximum overall average whitefly population was 2.14, 2.01, 2.48 and 2.86 whitefly/ leaf was recorded at 15, 30,45 and 60 days after transplanting (DAT), respectively in the crop transplanted on D₂ (02/02/2018). This was followed by the crop transplanted on D₃ (18/02/2018) which recorded overall average whitefly population of 1.77, 1.67, 2.27, and 2.47 whitefly/ leaf at 15, 30, 45 and 60 DAT, respectively. The crop transplanted on D₁ (17/01/2018) was found to suffer less by the tomato leaf curl virus of tomato observed at various interval was found to be significantly higher in the crop transplanted on 02/02/2018 (D₂); whereas, it was at par in the crop transplanted on 18/02/2018(D₃) and 17/01/2018(D₁).

Whitefly population and tomato cultivars

Result table 1 and 2 revealed that in both the tomato cultivars leaf curl whitefly population was varied with the transplanting dates and it was found to be increased steadily with age of the crop. Among the tomato cultivars grown in *Rabi* cv. Pusa Ruby (Susceptible) recorded comparatively maximum whitefly population of (D₃) 2.73/leaf and minimum whitefly population Arka Rakshak (tolerant) (D₃) 1.58/leaf at 60 days after transplanting. Similar in Summer Pusa Ruby (susceptible) recorded maximum whitefly population of (D₂) 3.24/leaf and minimum whitefly population Arka Rakshak (tolerant) (D₂) 2.48/leaf at 60 days of transplanting. In both tomato cultivars, cv. Pusa Ruby (susceptible) the whitefly population observed at various intervals was found to be significantly higher than that of Arka Rakshak (tolerant). Interaction effects (DxV) in respect of whitefly population were also found significant.

Disease incidence and planting dates

Result Table 3 and 4 revealed that in all the three planting dates during *Rabi* 2017-18 and Summer 2018-19 tomato leaf curl virus disease was first noticed appear after two weeks of transplanting of the tomato cultivars in the field. It was observed that the planting dates significantly influenced the percentage disease incidence in both of the tomato cultivars grown and was found to increase steadily with age of the crop. In *Rabi* crop planting three dates, significantly maximum overall average disease incidence was 4.63, 8.92, 14.99 and 22.47 percent was recorded at 15, 30, 45 and 60 days after transplanting (DAT), respectively in the crop transplanted on D₃ (18/11/2017). This was followed by the crop transplanted on D₂ (2/11/2017) which recorded overall average disease incidence of 3.21, 5.70, 12.49, and 18.92 percent at 15, 30, 45 and 60 DAT, respectively. The crop transplanted on D₁ (17/10/2017) was found to suffer less by the tomato leaf curl virus disease incidence observed at various interval was found to be significantly higher in the crop transplanted on 18/11/2017 (D₃); whereas, it was at par in the crop transplanted on 2/11/2017(D₂) and 18/11/2017(D₃). In Summer crop planting three dates, significantly maximum overall average disease incidence was 6.06, 7.85, 9.99 and 17.49 percent was recorded at 15, 30,45 and 60 days after transplanting(DAT), respectively in the crop transplanted on D₂ (02/02/2018). This was followed by the crop transplanted on D₃ (18/02/2018) which recorded overall average disease incidence of 3.57, 5.00, 8.57, and 14.94 percent at 15, 30, 45 and 60 DAT, respectively. The crop transplanted on D₁ (17/01/2018) was found to suffer less by the tomato leaf curl virus disease

incidence observed at various interval was found to be significantly higher in the crop transplanted on 02/02/2018 (D₂); whereas, it was at par in the crop transplanted on 18/02/2018(D₃) and 17/01/2018(D₁).

Disease incidence and tomato cultivars

Result Table 3, 4 revealed that in both the tomato cultivars leaf curl incidence was varied with the transplanting dates and it was found to be increased steadily with age of the crop. Among the tomato cultivars grown in *Rabi* cv. Pusa Ruby (susceptible) recorded comparatively maximum disease incidence of (D₃) 34.31 and minimum disease incidence Arka Rakshak (tolerant) (D₃) 5.71 percent at 60 days after transplanting. Similar in Summer Pusa Ruby (susceptible) recorded maximum disease incidence of (D₂) 28.57 and minimum disease incidence Arka Rakshak (tolerant) (D₂) 6.41 percent at 60 days of transplanting. In both tomato cultivars, disease cultivars Pusa Ruby (susceptible) the disease incidence observed at various intervals was found to be significantly higher than that of Arka Rakshak (tolerant). Interaction effects (DxV) in respect of disease incidence were also found significant.

Fruit yield during *Rabi* and Summer, 2018-19

Result Table 5reveled that during *Rabi* and Summer 2018-19 the fruit yield was found to be affected significantly in both the tomato cultivars planted at various date. However, in *Rabi* season significantly highest fruit yield in both tomato cultivars Pusa Ruby (91.8 q/ha) and Arka Rakshak (152.0 q/ha) was recorded in the crop planted on 17/10/2018 D₁ with least this was followed by the crop planted on 02/11/2018 D₂ which recorded fruit yield of 84.0 and 128.0q/ha, respectively in Pusa Ruby and Arka Rakshak. Comparatively minimum fruit yield of 73.0 q/ ha (Pusa Ruby) and 91.0 q/ ha (Arka Rakshak) was recorded in the crop planted on 18/12/2018(D₃). The fruit yield Arka Rakshak recorded in D₁ followed by D₂ was at par. Where as in Pusa Ruby it was at all the three planting dates. Highest overall average fruit yield (123.6 q/ha) was recorded in tomato cv. Arka Rakshak followed by Pusa Ruby (82.9q/ha). In Summer season Pusa Ruby (166.0 q/ha) and Arka Rakshak (182.0 q/ha) was recorded in the crop planted on 17/01/2019 (D₁). This was followed by the crop planted on 18/02/2019(D₂) which recorded fruit yield of 163.0 and 142.0 q/ ha respectively in Pusa Ruby. Comparatively minimum fruit yield of 118.0 q/ha (Pusa Ruby) and 149.0 q/ha (Arka Rakshak) was recorded in the crop planted on 02/02/2019 (D₃). The fruit yield recorded in D₁ and D₂ of both the tomato cultivars was at par with each other. Highest overall average fruit yield (166.0 q/ha) was recorded in tomato cv. Arka Rakshak followed by Pusa Ruby (141.0 q/ha).

The results present studies are in accordance with the results of different scientist who worked on this aspect. The effective time for planting of tomato October to Mid-December was the most effective time for planting of tomato followed by January to first March was reported by Saklani and Mathai(1977); Shaheen(1983); Ioannou and Iordanou (1985); Borah and Bordoloi (1998) reported that the minimum disease incidence and whitefly population were recorded in crop planted from October 10 to November 25. Mahajan (2001) reported the 1st September planting was found to be suitable to get the stable yield from tomato with minimum infection by ToLCV. In later dates of planting, though recorded less disease incidence but produce lower yield. Gupta *et al.* (2005) studied that the incidence of leaf curl virus disease of tomato (cv. Naveen) with relation to the planting dates (15 and 30 March, 14 and 29 April, and 15 May), the minimum disease incidence was recorded in the crop planted on 14 April and the incidence increased in linier progression in subsequent planting date. In order to effectively screen for TYLCV resistance under natural disease conditions, it is necessary to identify hotspots and favorable seasons (Dhaliwal *et al.*, 2020).

Correlation between whitefly population and tomato leaf curl virus disease at different planting date during *Rabi*, 2017

The correlation between whitefly population and disease incidence were found positive in both the tomato cv. (Pusa Ruby and Arka

Rakshak). The positive, statically significant correlations were found in between whitefly population and disease incidence in all planting date of tomato. Simple correlation coefficient between major weather parameters, whitefly population and disease incidence was worked out and the results obtained (Table 6) revealed that in both tomato cv. (Pusa Ruby and Arka Rakshak), the whitefly population and disease incidence was found to be influenced mostly by the temperature, relative humidity, rainfall and wind velocity. of the weather parameters, temperature (Max.) had negative and non-significant effect with Pusa Ruby and Arka Rakshak whitefly population and disease incidence were positive non-significant (Arka Rakshak) with whitefly population; where as temperature (min.) had negative and non-significant effect on disease incidence and whitefly population in both the tomato cultivars. Relative humidity am and pm had negative non-significant with white fly population and disease incidence in both varieties were relative humidity pm significant with whitefly population (Arka Rakshak). Wind velocity positively correlated with whitefly population (Pusa Ruby) were disease incidence (Arka Rakshak) non-significant and negatively correlation with white population (Arka Rakshak) were disease incidence (Pusa Ruby) no rainfall.

Correlation between whitefly population and tomato leaf curl virus disease at different planting date during Summer, 2018

The correlation between whitefly population and disease incidence were found positive in both the tomato cv. (Pusa Ruby and Arka Rakshak). The positive, statically significant correlations were found in between whitefly population and disease incidence in all planting date of tomato. Simple correlation coefficient between major weather parameters, whitefly population and disease incidence was worked out and the results obtained (Table 7) revealed that in both tomato cv. (Pusa Ruby and Arka Rakshak), the whitefly population and disease incidence was found to be influenced mostly by the temperature, relative humidity, rainfall and wind velocity.

of the weather parameters, temperature (maximum and minimum) was a significantly and non-significantly positively correlated with whitefly population and disease incidence with both varieties (Pusa Ruby and Arka Rakshak). The correlation of relative humidity AM and PM was negatively non-significant with whitefly population and disease incidence with both varieties. Relative humidity PM positively correlated with whitefly population and disease incidence with Arka Rakshak. Wind velocity and rainfall had non-significant positively relationship with whitefly population and disease incidence in both varieties were wind velocity negatively correlated with disease incidence in Arka Rakshak. The results of the present studies are correlated with the reports of different workers. Bharadwaj and Kushwaha (1984) who reported that the whitefly population had negative correlation with relative humidity (RH) and positive correlation with temperature in Rajasthan condition, where as Saikia and Muniyappa (1989a and 1989b) reported that a positive correlation between the incidence of TLCV disease and whitefly population is well documented and attempts were made to prevent the spread of the virus by controlling whitefly populations. Green and Kalloo (1994) reported that the epidemiology of whitefly transmitted geminiviruses is characterized by a close correlation between disease incidence and whitefly populations which often show strong seasonal fluctuations. Holt *et al.* (1999) reported that the *B. tabaci* population is highest during the hot season of February to May when temperatures are high and rainfall is low and ToLCVD incidence is positively correlated with it. From September to October, which is also the period of low temperatures and high rainfall, numbers fall to approximately a tenth of their Summer levels tomato leaf curl virus disease (ToLCVD) incidence in South India is highly correlated with the size of the *B. tabaci* population. Mirza *et al.* (2018) reported that four tomato cultivars i.e., Reo Grande, Roma, Moneymaker and Nagina were grown under field conditions to screen against TLCV. Correlation studies revealed a positive and significant relationship among TLCV, whitefly population and environmental factors

(temperature and relative humidity). Highest whitefly infestation with TLCV severity was observed on moneymaker compared to other tested cultivars. A significant negative correlation was found between catch and maximum and minimum temperature and a significant positive correlation with mean morning R. H. All the weather parameters collectively influenced the aleyrodid population from 42.9 to 70.6 per cent. Dhawan and Simwat (2021) found a substantial negative association between afternoon R. H. and the means minimum temperature among abiotic parameters. The moon's failures and a protracted drought combined with high temperatures are the main causes of the whitefly spread. Variations in the amount of food supplies appeared to have an impact on population swings.

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Table 1. Effect of planting dates/ season and tomato varieties on tomato leaf curl virus whitefly population and planting dates during Rabi, 2017

Date of transplanting (DAT)	Whitefly population/ leaf*											
	15 DAT			30 DAT			45 DAT			60 DAT		
	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean
D ₁ (17/10/2017)	1.63	0.7	1.16	1.87	0.87	1.37	1.87	0.91	1.39	2.12	0.91	1.51
D ₂ (2/11/2017)	1.47	0.84	1.15	1.77	0.99	1.38	1.95	1.08	1.51	2.27	1.12	1.69
D ₃ (18/11/2017)	1.87	0.96	1.41	2.04	1.01	1.52	2.54	1.22	1.88	2.73	1.58	2.15
	SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD	
DAT	0.31	0.93		0.28	0.83		0.42	1.27		0.43	1.28	
Variety	0.25	0.76		0.34	1.05		0.52	1.56		0.53	1.57	
Interaction	0.44	1.32		0.48	1.44		0.74	2.20		0.75	2.23	

*Values in parenthesis are square root ($\sqrt{X + 0.5}$) transformed values., V₁-Pusa Ruby (Susceptible), V₂-Arka Rakshak (Resistant), DAT –Days after transplanting

Table 2. Effect of planting dates/ season and tomato varieties on tomato leaf curl virus whitefly population and planting dates during, 2018

Date of transplanting (DAT)	Whitefly Population/leaf*											
	15 DAT			30 DAT			45 DAT			60 DAT		
	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean
D ₁ (17/01/2018)	1.95	0.91	1.43	2.04	1.08	1.56	2.12	1.74	1.93	2.41	1.77	2.09
D ₂ (02/02/2018)	2.34	1.95	2.14	2.67	1.35	2.01	3.02	1.95	2.48	3.24	2.48	2.86
D ₃ (18/02/2018)	2.19	1.35	1.77	2.12	1.22	1.67	2.67	1.87	2.27	2.67	2.27	2.47
	SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD	
DAT	0.31	0.93		0.45	1.35		0.74	2.22		0.52	1.56	
variety	0.25	0.76		0.55	1.66		0.91	2.72		0.64	1.91	
Interaction	0.44	1.32		0.79	2.34		1.29	3.84		0.90	2.70	

*Values in parenthesis are square root ($\sqrt{X + 0.5}$) transformed values.

V₁-Pusa Ruby (Susceptible), V₂-Arka Rakshak (Resistant)

DAT –Days after transplanting.

Table 3. Effect of planting dates and tomato cultivars on tomato leaf curl virus incidence during *Rabi*, 2017

Date of transplanting (DAT)	Percent disease incidence*											
	15 DAT			30 DAT			45 DAT			60 DAT		
	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean
D ₁ (17/10/2017)	2.14	0.71	1.42	4.28	1.42	2.85	9.99	2.13	6.06	17.13	4.28	10.70
D ₂ (2/11/2017)	5.71	0.71	3.21	8.56	2.85	5.70	19.99	4.28	12.49	32.14	4.96	18.92
D ₃ (18/11/2017)	7.85	1.42	4.63	14.28	3.56	8.92	25.71	4.99	14.99	34.31	5.71	22.47
	SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD	
DAT	0.59	1.80		0.61	1.88		0.76	2.33		1.25	3.81	
variety	0.48	1.47		0.50	1.53		0.62	1.90		1.02	3.11	
Interaction	0.83	2.54		0.87	2.66		1.08	3.30		1.77	5.39	

*Mean of replication, V₁-Pusa Ruby (Susceptible), V₂-Arka Rakshak (Resistant), DAT –Days after transplanting.

Table 4. Effect of planting dates and tomato cultivars on tomato leaf curl virus incidence during *Summer*, 2018

Date of transplanting (DAT)	Percent disease incidence*											
	15 DAT			30 DAT			45 DAT			60 DAT		
	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean	V ₁	V ₂	Mean
D ₁ (17/01/2018)	4.28	1.43	2.85	5.71	2.85	4.28	9.28	3.57	6.42	21.43	4.28	12.85
D ₂ (02/02/2018)	9.28	2.85	6.06	11.42	4.28	7.85	14.28	5.71	9.99	28.57	6.41	17.49
D ₃ (18/02/2018)	5.00	2.14	3.57	6.43	3.57	5.00	12.14	5.00	8.57	23.57	5.71	14.64
	SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD		SE±	CD	
DAT	0.54	1.61		0.60	1.80		0.74	2.20		1.57	4.60	
variety	0.66	1.91		0.74	2.20		0.90	2.69		1.92	5.73	
Interaction	0.94	2.79		1.05	3.12		1.28	3.81		2.72	8.10	

*Mean of replications, V₁-Pusa Ruby (Susceptible), V₂-Arka Rakshak (Resistant), DAT –Days after transplanting.

Table 5. Effect of planting date and tomato cultivars on fruit yield during *Rabi* and *Summer* season

<i>Rabi</i>	Fruit yield (q/ha)		Summer	Fruit yield (q/ha)	
	Pusa Ruby	Arka Rakshak		Pusa Ruby	Arka Rakshak
D ₁ (17/10/2017)	91.80	152.0	D ₁ (17/01/2018)	166.00	182.0
D ₂ (02/11/2017)	84.00	128.0	D ₂ (02/02/2018)	118.0	149.0
D ₃ (18/12/2017)	73.00	91.00	D ₃ (18/02/2018)	142.0	163.0
Overall Average	82.90	123.6	Overall Average	141.0	165.6
S.E±	8.50	6.20	S.E±	9.00	8.90
C.D.	25.0	18.20	C.D.	26.5	26.4

Table 6. Correlation of tomato leaf curls virus disease with its vector, varieties and weather parameter in Rabi

Variable/factors	Whitefly Population (Pusa Ruby)	Whitefly Population (Arka Rakashak)	Disease incidence (Pusa Ruby)	Disease incidence (Arka Rakashak)
Whitefly Population (Pusa Ruby)	1			
Whitefly Population (ArkaRakashak)	0.886	1		
Disease incidence (PusaRuby)	0.895	0.871	1	
Disease incidence (ArkaRakashak)	0.890	0.824	0.940	1
Temperature (MAX)oC	-0.136	0.080	-0.051	-0.166
Temperature (Min)oC	-0.395	-0.264	-0.402	-0.480
Relative humidity AM	-0.315	-0.500	-0.342	-0.323
Relative humidity PM	-0.436	-0.639	-0.571	-0.540
Wind velocity	0.0396	-0.0498	-0.059	0.0510

**Significant at 1%

Table 7. Correlation of tomato leaf curl virus disease with its vector, varieties and weather parameter in Summer

Variable/ Factor	Whitefly Population (Pusa Ruby)	Whitefly Population (Arka Rakashak)	Disease incidence (Pusa Ruby)	Disease incidence (Arka Rakashak)
Whitefly Population (Pusa Ruby)	1			
Whitefly Population (ArkaRakashak)	0.790	1		
Disease incidence (Pusa Ruby)	0.783	0.845	1	
Disease incidence (ArkaRakshak)	0.901	0.818	0.845	1
Rainfall	0.138	0.362	0.397	0.356
Temperature (MAX)oC	0.566	0.250	0.301	0.398
Temperature (Min)oC	0.670	0.539	0.368	0.623
Relative humidity AM	-0.548	-0.188	-0.206	-0.256
Relative humidity PM	-0.080	0.095	-0.033	0.112
Wind velocity	0.232	0.109	-0.0030	0.296

**Significant at 1%